

Generalizability of adoption barriers of smart home technology

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ABSTRACT

Global leading companies are launching smart home services and products based on Internet of Things (IoT). An element within smart homes is home-based eHealth. This is a technical development that improves healthcare locally, regionally and worldwide by using information and communication technology. However, the spread of smart homes has been slower than expected. This trend is declared by the influence of adoption barriers. In the Netherlands, the most influential adoption barriers are the expected cost of smart home devices, the fear of hacking and privacy issues. This research aimed to develop knowledge on the generalizability of the smart home adoption barriers from the home-based eHealth perspective. This research presents the findings of the expectation that measured adoption barriers of smart homes in general, are not representative compared to the adoption barriers of home-based eHealth. This research is based on the expectation that the different drivers are causing the non-generalizability.

Keywords

Smart homes, home-based eHealth, adoption barriers, smart sensor technology.

INTRODUCTION

Sanguinetti, Karlin and Ford (2017) address the fact that despite the abundance and variety of products, marketing efforts, and great expectations, awareness and adoption of smart home technology remains low. Greenough (2016) argues that the current market for smart homes finds itself in a ‘chasm’ between the early-adopters phase and the mass-market phase of adoption curve (see literature review for clarification on the adoption curve phases). This competitive market makes it even more crucial for organizations to differentiate

themselves. Clear insight on the adoption drivers and adoption barriers of smart home technology is therefore a prerequisite for succeeding in this market.

According to GfK, the interest in smart homes has declined from 59% in 2017 to 48% in 2018. This trend is extra alarming since the awareness of smart homes increased from 51% to 60% respectively. In other words, while the awareness is increasing, the interest is decreasing.

GfK identified three main adoption drivers for smart homes in general:

1. Convenience, 41%;
2. Energy savings, 40%;
3. Comfort, 32%.

GfK also identified three main adoption barriers for smart homes in general:

1. Expected cost to purchasing smart homes, 41%;
2. Fear of hacking, 36%;
3. Privacy issues, 36%.

These barriers of adoption are supported by Balta-Ozkan, Davidson, Bicket and Whitmarsh (2013). However, these barriers are determined for smart home technology in general.

Important to note, to avoid unclarities, is that the percentages mentioned above do not add up to 100%. This is because the mentioned adoption drivers and barriers are not exclusive. The percentages merely indicate the proportion of the times the drivers and barriers are mentioned.

The problem statement arises from the previously described business problem, and is with regard to the generalizability of the GfK findings in smart homes. Examining the generalizability calls for research on how different drivers of smart home technology affect the adoption barriers of smart homes and influence the interest rate. Expected is that adoption drivers and adoption barriers, for instance for home-

based eHealth (in this case study), deviate per area of application. People naturally want to stay healthy, and therefore we expect that the motivation behind the consideration to purchase home-based eHealth compared to for example smart home convenience technology is different. As well we expect that the adoption barrier ‘Cost’ is less important if the incentive is to stay healthy. The knowledge gap, that is aimed to fill, is the generalizability of the adoption drivers and adoption barriers for smart homes compared to its different applications. Smart home technology can be divided in multiple areas of application. In figure 1, an overview of different applications of smart home technology is displayed.

Figure 1: Overview smart home applications (Balta-Ozkan, et al., 2013)

Security, assisted living, health, entertainment, communication, convenience and comfort, and energy savings are the areas in which smart home technology can be deployed (Balta-Ozkan, et al., 2013). For every subgroup of smart homes, drivers and/or services are displayed in table 1 to elaborate on the opportunities brought by smart home technology (Srinivasan, Birchfield, Qian, & Kidane, 2005; Mendes, Godina, Rodrigues, Matias, & Catalão, 2015; Niyato, Lu, & Ping, 2011).

Table 1. Drivers of smart homes

	Smart sensor application
Security	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Movement monitoring; ● Alerts; ● Random lightning.
Assisted living	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Independence; ● Peace of mind; ● Monitoring of activities.
Health	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Health

	monitoring; <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Convenience; ● Medical expenses.
Entertainment	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Sound optimization; ● Game control; ● Virtual reality systems.
Communication	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Real-time tracking; ● Social communication; ● M2M-communication.
Convenience & comfort	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Central control; ● Finding objects; ● Automation.
Energy savings	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Monitoring abnormal activity; ● Heating efficiency; ● Electricity budgets.

Problem statement

From the aforementioned, the following research question is derived:

“To what extent are the adoption barriers of smart home technologies in general (as a whole) generalizable to the adoption barriers of home-based eHealth technologies, and how does this influence the interest rate in smart homes?”.

Important to note is that the study examines adoption drivers and adoption barriers from a consumer (end-user) perspective.

Sub-questions

1. What are the adoption barriers of smart home technology in general (descriptive), and what is their effect on the adoption of smart home technologies?;
2. What are the adoption barriers of home-based eHealth technology (descriptive), and what is their effect on the adoption of smart home technologies?;
3. What is the effect of different adoption drivers and barriers on the interest rate in smart homes?;

4. To what extent do the adoption barriers of smart home technology differ from the adoption barriers of home-based eHealth technology?;
5. To what extent do different drivers of adoption of home-based eHealth technology influence the composition of adoption barriers of home-based eHealth technology?;
6. To what extent are adoption drivers influential on the adoption of home-based eHealth technologies?;
7. To what extent do differences in the composition of adoption barriers influence the interest rate in smart home technology?

The purpose of this research is to provide insights in to what extent different drivers of applying smart home technologies influence the adoption of these technologies.

Relevance

With this case study we provide specific information concerning the adoption barriers of home-based eHealth. Companies within the smart home healthcare industry can use this information to adjust their strategy to better overcome these specific adoption barriers and to tailor their product-to-market strategy in such a way that interest in smart homes increases in the Netherlands. Svensson (2002) describes that the key issue to success in the marketplace is a thorough understanding of why consumers are willing to buy an organization's product.

Prior research measured adoption barriers of smart homes in general. There is a lack of knowledge in the adoption barriers concerning the different applications of smart homes. In this case study we investigated if the adoption barriers in general deviate when compared to home-based eHealth. With this study we provided new insights in adoption barriers of smart homes. Investigation is based on different drivers behind the adoption of smart home in general and home-based eHealth.

Theoretical framework

Literature review

A smart home is defined as a residence equipped with a high-tech network, linking sensors and domestic devices, appliances, and features that can be remotely monitored, accessed or controlled, and provide services that respond to the needs of its inhabitants. Smart homes technology can be applied for different reasons: security, assisted living, health, entertainment, communication, convenience

and comfort, and energy efficiency (Balta-Ozkan, et al., 2013).

The term eHealth is defined by Eysenbach (2001) as: "eHealth is an emerging field in the intersection of medical informatics, public health and business, referring to health services and information delivered or enhanced through the Internet and related technologies." The term not only characterises a technical development, but also a way of thinking to improve healthcare locally, regionally and worldwide by using information and communication technology (Oh, Rizo, Enkin, & Jadad, 2005). The concept of home-based eHealth is including both telehomecare and smart homes. The first one describes how technology can enhance current home care services. Telehomecare, also known as Home TeleHealth (HTH) can be described as the use of telecommunications by a home care provider to link patients or customers to one or more out-of-home sources of care information, education, or service by means of telephones, computers, interactive television, or some combination of each (Koch, 2006). The second one (smart homes) refer to non-obtrusive disease prevention and monitoring of residents who are not necessarily home care patients, such as, e.g. many elderly (Demiris, 2004).

In this study, the drivers of adoption can be seen as the most important incentives to adopt a certain technology. In this case, adoption drivers are incentives to invest in smart home technology as a whole. Adoption barriers within this research are treated as elements that block the adoption of smart home technology. They can be viewed as the counterpart of adoption drivers. Adoption barriers are incentives to not invest in smart home technology.

Previously mentioned is the chasm in which the smart home technology currently finds itself. This chasm is the space between the early-adopters phase and the mass-market phase. These phases are derived from the adoption curve (Rogers, 2003). This theory seeks to explain how, why and at what rate new technologies spread over time. It is important to understand in which of the phases a specific technology is in, since it alters the way a product should be brought to the marketplace.

Conceptual model

The underlying conceptual model of the research question is as follows:

Figure 2: Conceptual model

For a better understanding of the conceptual model, the variables are explained, after which elaboration is given to the (hypothesized) relationships between the variables.

The study examines which different drivers for adoption have an effect on previously examined adoption barriers. Research conducted by GfK resulted in three main drivers for the adoption of smart home technology: convenience, comfort and savings (energy).

Interest in smart homes is the dependent variable in the conceptual model. As stated in the business problem, there are 'general' drivers for smart home adoption. These drivers contribute to the adoption of smart homes. The mediating variable are adoption barriers. Home-based eHealth is a moderating variable in this research. The adoption drivers for eHealth (see table 1) give a positive/negative influence on the adoption barriers, and therefore on the interest in smart homes.

Hypotheses

We expect that the composition of adoption drivers and barriers are not generalizable, in the sense that we expect that the composition of these adoption drivers and barriers are different when measured from the perspective of different smart home technology applications. We address this by evaluating adoption drivers and barriers from a healthcare (home-based eHealth) perspective. We use home-based eHealth as a case study to give conclusions on our hypotheses.

Smart home drivers

H1: Smart home drivers are not generalizable to different areas of application.

Home-based eHealth drivers

H2: Home-based eHealth drivers differ from smart home drivers.

Adoption barriers

H3.1: Adoption barriers deviate if viewed from different perspectives (adoption barriers are different if viewed from a healthcare perspective).

Generalizability of adoption drivers and barriers of home-based eHealth

H3.2: The composition of adoption barriers for smart home technology are not generalizable to the composition of adoption barriers for home-based eHealth.

Interest in smart homes

H4: Different adoption drivers and different adoption barriers influence the interest rate in smart homes.

Research design

We started our correlational research with archival research. Archival research in the sense as literature review. We analyzed various academic papers to get a grasp of smart home technology, adoption drivers and adoption barriers. The archival research is a continuous process, since new insights are gathered throughout the proceedings of the research.

Next to the archival research, we have done survey research. A survey to understand why and why not people would invest in home-based eHealth technologies. We sent our survey to everyone in the sample size which consists of a of 1,001 Dutch respondents in the age category 18+. Those questioned are responsible for the larger purchases in the household and at least known with the term smart homes. To reach representative attendees this research has been conducted in collaboration with the Smart Home Society. This is an initiative of Uneto, VNI, Guilty People, GfK and BSH.

After receiving the data from the conducted survey, it was analyzed and turned into useful information. With this information we were able to answer the research question and sub-question. Treated topics during this survey were brand preference, subscription forms, purchase reasons (drivers), adoption barriers, virtual assistants, installation and future expectations. The questions of the conducted survey that was used for this research is largely based on the survey GfK held. This increases the justification to compare the results in a later stage. In this research the earlier mentioned topics are treated and extended with smart home applications.

Measurement methods

To gather the needed information we combined publicly available data with self-gathered data. As to the publicly available data, data on smart home adoption, barriers and smart home interest are gathered from the research agency GfK. After this, primary data is collected through survey research. After all data was collected, stored and organized, we compared the differences critically.

Based on the gathered data the Cronbach's alpha was calculated by manipulating multiple

measurements (adoption drivers of home-based eHealth). The following subjects were examined in the survey: Brand preference, subscription forms, adoption drivers, adoption barriers, virtual assistants, installation and future expectations. The results of the survey are reliable since it consisted of mostly qualitative questions.

By doing this on purpose we intended to minimize the level of society desired answers. Hereby we protected questions to influence the answers given by respondents. The survey results were analyzed by using a transactional analysis approach. Meaning, all authors labeled qualitative answers after which we compared the labels and categorized the drivers and barriers. This validity since multiple interpretations were given.

In our archival research we analyzed different articles about smart homes. This gave a solid base for starting our study. In our survey we used the same topics and sample size as GfK did in their survey. Therefore the drivers measured by GfK can be compared with the drivers we identified in our research. The sample size consisted of 1,001 respondents who are 18+ and all have different households the results are highly concrete. Hence, this measure is solid.

The advantage of field research via conducting a survey is that the results are from the real world and therefore the external validity is high. The sample size we used also gave a good external validity and generalizability. Because we asked 1,001 different respondents about subjects that are different between themselves, we created a lot of input from different angles. However the research does not cover things like, different age groups or different kinds of situations at home (e.g. financial situation). For instance, people who are at the age of 60 do have more risk of health issues but did not grow up with smart sensors. Or when households are buying a new house instead of a house from the 1960's the adoption of Home based eHealth is different. Hence, the external validity is high but the generalizability can be higher.

Results

Based on the survey, the following results were interpreted:

Table 2. Adoption drivers and barriers compared

	Smart home technology (in general)	Home-based eHealth technology
Adoption barriers	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Costs; ● Fear of hacking; ● Data privacy. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Data privacy; ● Expected costs; ● Essence.
Adoption drivers	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Convenience; ● Energy savings; ● Comfort. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Convenience; ● Health; ● Medical expenditures.

The outcomes of the survey show that data privacy, expected costs and essence are the most important barriers for Home-based eHealth.

The most important drivers for Home-based eHealth are convenience, health and medical expenditures.

There are multiple remarkable outcomes from our survey. Firstly, 75% of the respondents does not know what Home-based eHealth is without any explanation. Secondly, 83% of the people who do not know what Home-based eHealth is, do think Home-based eHealth is something to consider. Also the respondents seem to see the costs as a barrier to adopt home based eHealth, but also as a driver since it can lower the medical expenditures.

In this section meaning is given to the results derived from the survey research. Meaning is given by interpreting the results and relating them back to our hypotheses.

We can conclude that our first hypothesis is true. With our case study on the adoption drivers of home-based eHealth we display (see table 2) that adoption drivers differ if smart home technology has a specific field of application (in our case home-based eHealth). The second hypothesis is partly correct, partly not. Convenience is in general and in the case of home-based eHealth the main adoption driver. Hence, we can conclude that it is above all important that the new technology provides improvements in convenience. The correctness of the second hypothesis comes from adoption driver two and three. As expected, home-based eHealth has different drivers. "Health" and "Medical Expenditures" are the second and third most important drivers of adoption. From the results of our survey, we concluded that continuous health monitoring is the second most important incentive to

invest in home-based eHealth technology. Medical expenses are related to the decrease of monthly insurance costs. Continuous health monitoring enables consumer to more specifically choose their insurances, based on their activities.

Our third hypothesis, concerning the adoption barriers of smart home technologies cannot significantly be concluded. Two of the three main barriers, as defined by GfK, are generalizable to home-based eHealth. There is, however, a slight deviation in the composition of the barriers. Data privacy and expected costs are still part of the three main barriers. But deployment of smart home technologies with a healthcare incentive results in the fact that data privacy becomes more important than expected costs.

If we relate our findings to our main research question: *“To what extent are the adoption barriers of smart home technologies (as a whole) generalizable to the adoption barriers of home-based eHealth technologies, and how does this influence the interest rate in smart homes?”*. We come up with the following answer. The drivers of smart home technology in general are in comparison to the drivers of home-based eHealth, not generalizable. Also can be concluded that different drivers cause different adoption barriers and therefore also the interest and adoption in smart homes.

Limitations and future research

The research presented in this paper is based on a former study of GfK about the adoption barriers of smart homes in general in the Netherlands. To ensure justification of comparing the results with this former study, the same sample population with additional criteria has been used. However, the findings presented above are not representative for countries apart from the Netherlands. Considering cultural differences, it is expected that the results in other countries differ in comparison to the Netherlands. Therefore, more comparative work needs to be done to examine the adoption barriers of home based eHealth in other countries.

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